

JOINT SOURCE AND CHANNEL RATE ALLOCATION FOR VIDEO TRANSMISSION OVER ERASURE CHANNELS

X. Hénoq, C. Guillemot and F. Le Léannec

INRIA/IRISA, Campus de Beaulieu,

35042 Rennes Cedex, FRANCE

Tel: +33 2.99.84.74.31 ; fax: +33 2.99.84.25.31

e-mail: `xavier.henoq@irisa.fr`

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a joint source and channel rate allocation algorithm for video transmission over erasure channels. The approach relies on unequal error protection (UEP) of the video stream, in order to minimize the received signal distortion. It takes into account both the frames and the channel characteristics. The loss behavior is approximated by a two states Markov model. The algorithm is incorporated in a H.263 version 2 compliant encoder. The encoder supports in addition a TCP-compatible (TCPC) congestion control mechanism and adapts the coding mode of each macro-block (MB) to the network loss behavior. Rate-distortion models are introduced in order to reduce the computational cost. A new payload format is also described for the transport of the streams over RTP. The overall approach, compared against equal error protection and against FEC -forward error correction- adapted to the channel only, leads to improved PSNR performance, with a more stable video quality.

1 INTRODUCTION

Delivering delay-constrained and high rate multimedia streams over the current Internet which does not offer any guarantee in terms of bandwidth, packet loss or delay is a very challenging issue for the networking and the coding research community. The IETF is currently studying models and architectures for supporting differentiated services, in order to better meet multimedia streams QoS requirements. Nevertheless, before becoming reality, the support of differentiated services requires the deployment of admission control mechanisms and of new queuing disciplines in the network nodes. A second trend consists in trying to adapt the applications to the network characteristics. By handling delay, packet loss, and source rate, the quality of multimedia communications over a best-effort Internet can be improved.

In order to improve the apparent quality of the transmission, error control mechanisms, such as Forward Error Correction (FEC) can be incorporated in the application layer. Redundant data is transmitted along with the original data, so that some of the lost original

data can be recovered from the redundant information. The redundant information can be generated by parity codes possessing the MDS property (e.g. Reed-Solomon (RS) codes [5]). Considering error control mechanisms, a key problem to be addressed is the optimal splitting of the bandwidth between the raw and the redundant data. Besides, compressed streams are characterized by segments containing information with different priority levels. The loss of the different segments will lead to different quality impairments. This led us to consider unequal error protection (UEP) of segments of the video signal, taking into account both the signal and the channel characteristics.

The approach developed here consists in adapting jointly the source and the redundancy rate to varying signal and channel characteristics, in order to minimize the overall distortion of the received signal. Targeting real-time applications, the computational cost of the algorithm is decreased, in a second step, by introducing rate-distortion models of the quantizers [6], [9]. Existing RTP payload formats [7], [2], being not suited for supporting unequal protection, a new format is proposed. The design is inspired from the PET - Priority Encoding Transmission - approach [1]. However, unlike the PET approach, the packetization process is coupled with the encoding in order to avoid slice fragmentation, therefore to guarantee a higher loss resilience. The channel rate adjustment granularity and the degree of interleaving, inherent to the transport format, can be flexibly traded against decreased latency.

The algorithm has been incorporated in a robust H.263 version 2 compliant video encoder supporting a TCPC congestion control [4] as well as a coding mode selection that can adapt to source and channel characteristics [3]. The quality benefits of the UEP algorithm with the corresponding transport format have been assessed against equal error protection (EEP) and against a FEC mechanism adapted only to the channel loss rate. Experimentation results show better performances, with a more stable quality, as a better bandwidth usage is achieved for both the source and the redundant data.

2 JOINT RATE ALLOCATION BETWEEN SOURCE AND CHANNEL

A temporal prediction mechanism, adaptive to both the signal and channel characteristics, has been described in [3]. It allows to select, for a group of MB $\mathcal{X} = \{X_1, \dots, X_N\}$ the combination of modes taken in $\mathcal{I} = \{INTRA, INTER, UNCODED\}$ so that the global distortion (source plus channel) is minimal under a given rate constraint predicted by a TCP-compatible (TCPC) congestion control mechanism. Considering in addition the usage of FEC, the problem addressed here is the optimal splitting of the predicted bandwidth between raw and redundant data.

In the Internet, the application has to deal mainly with erasures or missing packets. The exact position of missing data being known, a good correction capacity can be obtained by systematic MDS codes. An (n, k) MDS - Maximal Distance Separable - code takes k data packets and produces $n - k$ redundant data packets. The MDS property allows to recover up to $n - k$ losses in a group of n packets. Assuming that losses are independent, the effective average loss probability after channel decoding $P_{eff}(k)$ is given by

$$P_{eff}(k) = P_e \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \binom{n-1}{j} P_e^{n-1-j} (1 - P_e)^j, \quad (1)$$

where p_e is the average loss probability on the channel.

Given a loss model and the corresponding probabilities, an optimal splitting of the available bandwidth between raw and redundant data can be achieved by minimizing the global distortion defined as the sum of the quantization distortion and of the distortion induced by the channel residual losses. This leads to two embedded optimizations, expressed as the minimization of the cost function

$$\min_{\frac{k}{n}} J\left(\frac{k}{n}\right), \quad (2)$$

under a global rate constraint (source + channel) for the frame considered. The cost function $J\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)$ is defined by

$$J\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) = \min_{M, Q} \sum_{i=1}^L W(M_i) D(X_i, M_i, \frac{k}{n}, QP_i) + \lambda \cdot \frac{k}{n} \sum_{i=1}^L R(X_i, M_i, QP_i). \quad (3)$$

The term L represents the number of MB in an image. $D(X_i, M_i, \frac{k}{n}, QP_i)$ and $R(X_i, M_i, QP_i)$ denote respectively the distortion and the rate obtained by encoding the MB X_i with the mode M_i and the quantification step QP_i , under a source rate constraint of $\frac{k}{n} \sum_{i=1}^L R(X_i, M_i, QP_i)$, for a given frame. $W(i)$ is a weighting factor which reflects the relative priorities of the MB. A P-frame containing a higher number of INTRA-coded MB will be better protected. The term

$\frac{k}{n}$ represents the MDS code rate used for protecting the current frame. Note that for I-frames (INTRA frames), the cost function can be simplified since there is only one possible coding mode.

In the following, the Elliott-Gilbert model has been adopted to represent the loss process in the network. This model is a two-states Markov process (Received state and Lost state) characterized by the transition probabilities p and q between the received and the lost states, and by the probabilities $1 - p$ and $1 - q$ of remaining respectively in the received and in the lost states. The distortion of the MB X_i^t encoded in INTRA is then given by

$$D(X_i^t, Intra, k) = (1 - P_{eff}(k)) \|X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^t\| + P_{eff}(k) \|X_i^t - \tilde{X}_i^t\|, \quad (4)$$

where $\|X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^t\|$ denotes the MSE between the original MB X_i^t at spatial location i in the frame t and its quantized version $\hat{X}_i^t$. $\|X_i^t - \tilde{X}_i^t\|$ denotes the MSE between the original MB X_i^t and the concealed version $\tilde{X}_i^t$ of $\hat{X}_i^t$ when a loss occurs. The average effective loss probability is derived as in equation 1, where P_e is the average loss probability given by $\frac{p}{p+q}$. The concealment method used consists in replacing the current MB by the last MB received at the same spatial location in a previous frame.

Similarly, considering the total number of packets since the last INTRA-coded MB at the spatial location i , and assuming that the difference between two MB at the same spatial location i increases with their temporal distance, the distortion of an INTER-coded MB can be upper bounded by

$$D(X_i^t, Inter, k) \leq TDB(k) \|X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^t\| + BER(k) \|X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^{t_I}\|, \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{X}_i^{t_I}$ represents the last INTRA-coded MB at spatial location i . BER is the block error rate defined by [5]

$$BER(k) = \sum_{m=n-k+1}^n P(m, n), \quad (6)$$

where $P(m, n)$, called block error density function, gives the probability to have m losses within a block of n packets. This function can be expressed as

$$P(m, n) = \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-m+1} P_e G(\nu) R(m, n - \nu + 1), \quad 1 \leq m \leq n, \quad (7)$$

where $R(m, n)$ is the probability of $m - 1$ packet losses within the next $n - 1$ packets following a lost packet, given by

$$R(m, n) = \begin{cases} G(n), & m = 1, \\ \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-m+1} g(\nu) R(m - 1, n - \nu), & 2 \leq m \leq n \end{cases}$$

The functions $g(\nu)$ and $G(\nu)$ give respectively the probability of a gap (error-free interval) length ν and of a gap greater than $\nu - 1$. These functions are given by

$$g(\nu) = \begin{cases} 1 - q, & \nu = 1 \\ q(1 - p)^{\nu-2}p, & \nu > 1 \end{cases}$$

$$G(\nu) = \begin{cases} 1, & \nu = 1 \\ q(1 - p)^{\nu-2}, & \nu > 1 \end{cases}$$

The term $TDB(k)$ denotes the probability that k packets will be recovered. Its value can be derived from the block error density function by the relation

$$TDB(k) = \sum_{m=0}^{n-k} P(m, n). \quad (8)$$

The computational cost of the algorithm can be significantly reduced by using rate distortion modeling of the quantization performance. Two rate-distortion models [6] and [9] of the H.263 version 2 quantizer have been studied and led to the choice of an hybrid model relying on the rate model described in [6] and of the distortion model proposed in [9].

3 TRANSPORT WITH RTP

Several payload formats have been defined by the IETF for the transport of FEC data [7] and of video compressed streams [2]. However, none of them is amenable to the transport of unequally protected streams. A robust packetization method, inspired from the PET technique [1], but preventing in addition slice or GOB fragmentation, is described. Here, the construction of the slices delimited by markers and the packetization are coupled with the above joint source and channel coding algorithm. Images are fragmented across several consecutive packets and pieces of consecutive images and/or redundant data are grouped in the same RTP packet, as illustrated in Fig.1.

Let n be both the number of packets needed to transport one image and the number of symbols generated by the channel encoding. The parameter k varies for each image in the interval $[\frac{n}{2}, n]$. Let R_c be the bit budget for a given image. The algorithm described above allows to choose, on a MB basis, the coding mode (INTRA or INTER), the quantization parameter QP and the parameter k . The average size of a slice is calculated by R_c/k . The image is encoded MB by MB. When the cumulated bit rate for a set of MB reaches the value of the average size of a slice, a synchronization marker is introduced in the bit stream. The slices of a given image are then spread over different RTP packets as shown in Fig.1. The slices of consecutive images are grouped in the same packet until reaching the MTU - maximum transfer unit - size. The format leads naturally to an interleaving of the data which disperses the effect of the packet losses.

Figure 1: Transport format.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the experiments reported here, we have taken $W_{INTRA} = 5$, $W_{INTER} = 2$, $W_{UNCODED} = 1$ as distortion weighting factors. The channel is characterized by the transition probabilities $p = 0.08$ and $q = 0.6$. The MDS code applied is a Reed-Solomon code with $n = 32$ and $k \in [16, 32]$. Fig.(2) shows the PSNR curves obtained when encoding the CIF (30 frames/s) sequence 'coast-guard' under an overall bandwidth constraint of 384 kbits/s, with three encoders: 1) a compliant H.263 + supporting the source and channel adaptive FEC-UEP scheme described above, 2) a compliant H.263 + supporting only the coding mode selection mechanism described in [3], and 3) a simple channel adaptive FEC mechanism. In the later, the parameter k of the Reed-Solomon code is chosen so that, given the channel characteristics ($p = 0.08$ and $q = 0.6$), all the packets lost in a group of $n = 32$ packets can be recovered (i.e. $k = 26$). Those results show better performances, with a more stable quality, as a better bandwidth usage is achieved for both the source and the redundant data.

Figure 2: Comparative results between 1)- FEC-UEP adapted to both source and channel, 2)- adaptive mode selection, 3)- FEC adapted to channel only (sequence 'Coast-guard')

Experiments have also been carried out in order to estimate the benefits of FEC-UEP over equal error protection of the whole video stream (EEP), with the same en-

coder (i.e. supporting TCP-friendly congestion control and adaptive mode selection). In the EEP experiment, the value of the parameter k of the Reed-Solomon code has been fixed to an average value obtained when performing the UEP over the whole sequence. Fig.(3) shows the PSNR curves obtained by the FEC-UEP approach and by the EEP approach with the sequence 'Stefan' for an overall bandwidth constraint of 900 kbit/s , with $n = 32$ and $n = 10$. The curves show a clear advantage in adopting an UEP strategy, especially for sequences with a lot of activity (e.g. high motion).

Figure 3: Comparison between UEP and EEP and impact of the parameter n on the quality(sequence 'Stefan')

The choice of the parameter n of the Reed-Solomon code has obviously an impact on the delay. Indeed, there is a trade-off between the flexibility for adjusting the protection rate (i.e. number of possible k/n values) and the delay induced by the FEC mechanism. We have considered first $n = 32$, hence a protection rate k/n in $\{1, 31/32, 15/16, 29/32, \dots, 1/2\}$, and a CIF (30 frames/s) sequence encoded under an overall bandwidth constraint of 384 kbits/s . We have also chosen an MTU size of 576 bytes. The proposed transport format leads to a delay of 7 frames (233 milliseconds). This value, to be added to the transmission, encoding and decoding delays is too high for interactive applications.

We have then taken $n = 10$. The delay induced by the protection mechanism falls to 3-4 frames (130 milliseconds, delay comparable to the delay induced by the hierarchical FEC proposed in [8]), while maintaining a stable video quality (see Fig.(3)). Note that, for lower values of n (e.g. $n = 10$), the granularity for adjusting the raw data rate becomes coarser. This leads the encoder rate control mechanism to reduce the frame rate, in order to obtain the best trade-off between quantization fineness and temporal resolution.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The problem addressed here is the optimal splitting of the available bandwidth between raw data and redun-

dant data. The algorithm described, based on an UEP of segments of the video streams, adapts this bandwidth share to both the time-varying source and network characteristics. The optimization procedure is simplified by using rate-distortion models. An ad hoc format has also been defined for the transport of the unequally protected streams over RTP. The packetization procedure, unlike the PET technique, coupled with the joint source and channel encoding, preserves from slice fragmentation, hence improves the loss resilience. The transport format still improves the loss resilience by naturally interleaving the blocks of data (i.e. video slices). The degree of interleaving as well as the granularity of channel rates can be flexibly adjusted and traded against decreased latency. Experimentation results show better PSNR performances and a more stable visual quality. Current work is dedicated to the extension of the approach to a layered multicast scenario.

References

- [1] A. Albanese, J. Blomer, J. Edmonds, M. Luby, and M. Sudan. Priority encoding transmission. *IEEE transactions on information theory*, 42(6):1737–1743, November 1996.
- [2] C. Bormann, L. Cline, G. Deisher, T. Gardos, C. Maciocco, D. Newell, J. Ott, S. Wenger, and C. Zhu. An RTP payload format for the 1998 version of ITU-T Rec. H.263 video (H.263+). Internet Engineering Task Force, Internet draft, may 1999.
- [3] F. Le Léanec and F. Toutain and C. Guillemot. Packet loss resilient MPEG-4 compliant video coding for the internet. *Journal Image Communication, Special issue on 'Real-time video over the Internet'*, (15):35–56, september 1999.
- [4] S. Floyd, M. Handley, J. Padhye, and J. Widmer. Equation-based congestion control for unicast applications. <http://www.aciri.org/tfrc/>, February 2000.
- [5] B. Girod, K. Stuhlmuller, M. Link, and U. Horn. Packet loss resilient internet video streaming. In *Proceedings of the SPIE conference on visual communications and image processing, VCIP'99*, pages 833–844, 1999.
- [6] J. Ribas-Corbera and S. Lei. Rate control for low-delay video communications. Technical report, ITU-Telecommunications Standardization Sector, Video coding expert group, 1997.
- [7] J. Rosenberg and H. Schulzrinne. An RTP payload format for generic forward error correction. Internet Engineering Task Force, Internet draft, february 1999.
- [8] W. Tan and A. Zakhor. Multicast transmission of scalable video using receiver-driven hierarchical fec. In *Proceedings of the packet video workshop, PVW'99*, April 1999.
- [9] K. H. Yang, A. Jacquin, and N. S. Jayant. Normalized rate-distortion model for H263-compatible codecs and its application to quantizer selection. In *proceedings of the IEEE International conference on image processing, ICIP'97*, october 1997.